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Utilization of funds allocated for Swachh Bharat Mission-Gramin and its impact in the state of Gujarat

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Abstract

Swachh Bharat Mission, a national level campaign, launched by the Government of India is a foremost step towards the protection of degrading environment. The objectives of the campaign include elimination of open defecation, conversion of insanitary toilets to pour flush toilets, eradication of manual scavenging and above all to bring about a behavioral change in people regarding healthy sanitation practices and to ensure public participation in achieving these objectives. Globally, India continues to be the country with highest number of people practicing open defecation. If Swachh Bharat Mission (SBM) is implemented properly with all its stakeholders taking their respective responsibilities, there is no wonder that one day India will become an open defecation free country. A brief about this programme, objectives & components of funds allocation in various years in different activities and outcomes of Comptroller and Auditor General's report has been discussed in this paper. The result found in Joint field visit of CAG regarding non-availability of water connection and soak pit in 41 villages and 15 out of 30 villages were not using toilets due to incomplete construction. Gujarat State has been declared Open defecation free in 2016-2017 by Hon. President of India. In this paper researcher will review Financial aspect of Swachh Bharat Mission-G of last five years i.e. 2014 to 2019 and Findings of Field visit reports of CAG with reference to proper utilization of funds and its effectiveness of Programme.

Key Words: 1.Comptroller and Auditor General, 2.Manual scavenging. 3. Open defecation, 4.Swachh Bharat Mission-Gramin.

Introduction:

Mahatma Gandhi, The Father of nation said "Sanitation is more important than independence". Proper sanitation and health practices are important for healthy nation and are integral parts of Global position of India. India's image of open defecation in public places that ruins the image on global platform and SBM-G addresses such important area. Prevalence of unsafe sanitary conditions faced by many countries and it reflect to their social and economic development of their national development. Countries of first world have highly safe drinking water and best sanitation practices and lower diseases faced by citizens. Swachh Bharat Mission-G was started in 2014 to achieve all round universal coverage by 150th Birth Anniversary of Mahatma Gandhi, 2019. This Flagship programme is considered as a largest sanitation campaign in all over the world and also emphasis on BCC (Behavioral Change Communication) plan for its effective implementation.

99.2% rural population are covered in throughout this five years of time and almost 10 Crore Toilets were constructed as per Base line survey 2012 and all most 5.65 Lac Villages have been declared open defecation free by self or third party validation. Certain benefit like Health to social dignity and other aspects has been improved in these years and gained its importance on a large scale. Sanitation on global level also gained attention by inclusion of Sustainable Development Goal's for which cleanliness tagged as universal area to cover by all nations. Total sum of 51314.3 Crore has been allotted to states for rural sanitation and out of that 47875.94 Crore has been released at various level but reports by various agencies and CAG indicates that the amount was unspent or Not Properly utilized by government & objectives has not been fulfilled.

Various Components for Swachh Bharat Mission-Gramin

1. Start-Up Activities

- Updating baseline survey - Conducting preliminary survey to assess the status of sanitation and hygiene practices
- Orientation of key personnel at the district/GP level and preparation of District Plans
- Preparation of State Plan (Programme Implementation Plan – PIP)

2. Information, Education, Communication (IEC)

The Swachh Bharat Mission (Gramin) is not about constructing toilets but aims at behavior change of the masses to adopt better sanitation practices. Therefore, information, education and communication (IEC) strategies, planning and their effective implementation is the key to the success of Swachh Bharat. Thus, IEC activities are not to be treated as 'standalone' activity as a 'component' of SBM-G, but the SBM-G is largely about effective IEC to nudge communities into adopting safe and sustainable sanitation practices.

3. Capacity Building

This component is for building capacities of stakeholders and sanitation workers, the Swachhagrahis/Sena, members of PRIs, VWSCs, functionaries of BPMU, DWSM, ASHA, Anganwadi workers, SHG members, masons, CSOs/NGOs, etc. The training may be on various approaches of IEC promoting behavioral change including Triggering (CAS), IPC and House to House communication etc., masonry work, plumbing, construction and maintenance of toilets, and for Solid and Liquid Waste Management works.

4. Construction of Individual Household Latrines

A duly completed household sanitary latrine unit shall comprise of sanitary sub structure that safely confines human faeces and eliminates the need for human handling before it is fully decomposed), ii) a super structure with water facility, and hand wash unit for cleaning and hand washing. The Mission aims to ensure that all rural families have access to safe toilets and therefore safe technology options are an important component of toilet choice. There are various safe sanitation technologies available like the Twin Pit, Septic Tank with soak pit, Eco-san, Bio toilets amongst others. The Ministry encourages the promotion of Twin-Pit technology for most parts of the country, however States may look to develop other safe technologies as well, and States shall disseminate information about available technologies and their costs to the beneficiary to enable him/her to make an informed choice.

5. Availability of Sanitary Material - through Rural Sanitary Marts, Production Centers, Self Help Groups

In many States, good quality sanitary material and hardware are accessible through the market with the private sector providing such material competitively. In such States RSMs/PCs are not required. However in a few States, the penetration of sanitary materials in the market is still inadequate. In such cases, States can decide to utilize the provision of the Rural Sanitary Marts (RSM) and Production Centers (PC). The Rural Sanitary Mart (RSM) is an outlet dealing with the material, hardware and designs required for the construction of sanitary latrines, soakage and compost pits, vermin composting, washing platforms, certified domestic water filters and other sanitation and hygiene accessories. The primary aim of an RSM is to provide materials, services and guidance needed for constructing different types of latrines and other sanitary facilities in close proximity to the beneficiaries. RSMs need to ensure that a variety of pans (Rural, ceramic, HDP, fiberglass) are available for the beneficiaries at reasonable rates. RSM should especially have those items required as a part of the sanitation package. It is a commercial venture with a social objective.

6. Provision of Revolving Fund in the District

A Revolving Fund may be created at the district level out of the SBM (G) funds. The Revolving Fund may be given to Societies, Self Help Groups or other groups as decided by the States, whose credit-worthiness

is established for providing cheap finance to their members, for the construction of toilets. Loan from this fund should be recovered in 12-18 installments. States will have the flexibility to decide other terms and conditions for sanction of the Revolving fund.

7. Micro Financing of Construction of Toilets

To enable the provision of low cost financing to individual households for the construction of household latrines and to leverage the network of NGOs and SHGs identified by agencies like NABARD and other financial institutions, in the wake of the need for universalization of sanitation facilities, possibilities of setting up a micro-financing arrangement should be explored by the States and the MDWS. This will facilitate converging financial resources, management skills and outreach capabilities to cover the demand of toilets for households not eligible for direct incentives under SBM (G), and/or for those households interested to build a more expensive toilet.

8. Community Sanitary Complex

Community Sanitary Complexes comprising of an appropriate number of toilet seats, bathing cubicles, washing platforms, wash basins, etc. can be set up in the village at allocation acceptable and accessible to all. Ordinarily, such complexes shall be constructed only when there is lack of land in the village for construction of household toilets and the Community/GP owns up to the responsibility of their operation and maintenance and raises a specific demand for the same. Such Complexes can be developed at public places, markets, bus stands, etc., where large scale congregation of people takes place.

9. Equity and inclusion

Equity and inclusion are of significance in the sanitation and hygiene sector. Providing access to the different categories of people who are not able to access and use safe sanitation facilities shall be a priority of the implementing agencies. Women, children, people of certain castes, faiths and ethnicities, older people, pregnant women, people with disabilities, geographically marginalized populations in remote areas, as well as those living in areas where it is difficult to construct simple toilets due to high water tables, sandy soils or hard rock may be given priority while planning for coverage. These categories of people may also include, among others, those who are socially and economically marginalized and those who are unable to use sanitation facilities constructed with standard designs. Requirements and sensitivities relating to gender including dignity and safety issues shall be taken into account at each stage of planning, implementation and post implementation management of sanitation issues.

10. Solid and Liquid Waste Management

The objective of SBM (G) is to bring about improvement in the cleanliness, hygiene and the general quality of life in rural areas. Solid and Liquid Waste Management (SLWM) is one of the key components of the programme to create clean villages. To this end, it is essential that the IEC interventions focus on Solid and Liquid Waste Management so as to create a felt need for these activities among the population. This must lead to the setting up of systems for scientific disposal of waste in such a way that has a tangible impact on the population. The Community /Gram panchayat has to be motivated to come forward, demand such a system, and subsequently operate and maintain.

11. Administrative Charges

States shall be permitted to utilize funds under this component as per requirement. The Administrative Charges shall normally permit expenditure on salary of temporary staff and agencies deployed for the execution of various components of the SBM(G) at State, District, Block and GP levels, support services, fuel charges, vehicle hire charges, stationery, monitoring & evaluation activities, TA/DA to Inter-State and Inter-District survey teams deputed for monitoring and verification, and exposure visits. (Ministry of Drinking water & Sanitation, 2017).

Methodology

This study is purely based on secondary data wherein researchers have tried to describe the concern in systematic and appropriate manner. For the same guidelines and reports on related topic have been studied.

Significance of the Study:-

Since SBM-G is flagship program of government of India to eradicate open defecation and promoting safe sanitation to citizens. SBM-G is one of the programmes supported by World Bank and other funding agencies for promoting proper infrastructure and strengthening existing sanitation policies in India.

As Government is taking initiatives for safe and healthy environment for Indian citizens by launching this very nature of programmes, it is imperative to observe the implementation and execution. It is also important to probe and evaluate the accountability and financial mechanism as well.

Hence, researchers developed the keen interest to compare and analyze the financial aspect on the impact and effectiveness of SBM-G.

Objectives:

- To evaluate the outcomes and recommendations of CAG reports.
- To compare and analyze financial mechanism & accountability for implementation of SBM-G Programme.
- To analyze the effectiveness & impact of Programme.

Scope of the study:

The conclusions derived from the study focuses on financial allotment and its utilizations for various purposes. This study will be helpful in understanding the outcomes and suggest possible interventions for effective execution.

Data Analysis:

To analyze & reach to the conclusion, researchers have referred various guidelines and reports related to SBM-G and Secondary data have been utilized for analysis.

Table 1: Sanitation Coverage at household level from 2011 to 2017

Sources: -Joint Monitoring Programme Report 2017

In October 2014, the Prime Minister of India launched an ambitious national sanitation programme that aims to eliminate open defecation by 2019. The Swachh Bharat Mission (SBM) has unprecedented political support and has mobilized nearly 17, 87,90,00,00,000 INR from Government, the private sector

and civil society. The rural programme promotes pour flush twin-pit toilets, which are designed to contain wastes in situ until they are safe to handle. The programme targets behavior change and community approaches to sanitation are being adopted throughout the country. The SBM has developed a national database with detailed information on latrine coverage down to the household level and a multi-stage verification.

As of June 2017, according to the SBM, over 205,000 villages, 149 districts and five States had reported themselves to be open-defecation free (ODF). The Government estimated that since the start of the Mission, in October 2014, coverage of latrines in rural India has increased from 42% to 65%, and the number of rural Indians defecating in the open had come down from 550 to 330 million people by June 2017.

The SBM programme recognizes the need to go beyond reporting infrastructure coverage, and is conducting population-based surveys to determine household use of sanitation facilities, which is the internationally agreed-upon indicator, used by Joint Monitoring Program to compare progress across countries. The National Annual Rural Sanitation Survey (NARSS) will generate up-to-date data on progress towards elimination of open defecation and trigger rewards for areas that have achieved targets (WHO & Unicef, 2017).

Table 2: Year wise Funds allocation for Swachh Bharat Mission- Gramin

(Sources: - Data.gov.in)

Table 2: Indicates funds allotment by government of India in various financial years. SBM-Gramin Launched in 2014 by Hon. Prime Minister of India. It all start with 2850 Crore in financial year of 2014-15 and 2730.3 Crore has been utilized under SBM-Gramin scheme it means almost 95.8% fund Utilized. In 2015-16, 6525 Crore allotted in financial year of 2015-16 and 6362.96 Crore has been utilized under SBM-Gramin scheme it means almost 97.51% funds Utilized. In 2016-17, 10513 Crore allotted in financial year of 2016-17 and 10271.96 Crore has been utilized under SBM-Gramin scheme it means almost 97.69% funds Utilized. In 2017-18, 16846.27 Crore allotted in financial year of 2017-18 and 16610.88 Crore has been utilized under SBM-Gramin scheme it means almost 98.60% funds Utilized. In 2018-19, 14478.03 Crore allotted in financial year of 2018-19 and 11900.11 Crore has been utilized under SBM-Gramin scheme it means almost 82.19% funds Utilized (Open Government Data).

Table 3: Financial Components of SBM-Gramin

Head	Centre Share	State Share	Beneficiaries	Amount as a % of SBM-G amount
IEC, Startup activities, ETC	60%	40%	-	8%
Revolving Fund	60%	40%	-	Up to 5%
Construction of Household Toilets	60% (7200/-)	40% (4800/-)	-	Amount required for full coverage
Community Sanitary Complexes	60%	30%	10%	Amount required for full coverage
Solid/Liquid Waste Management	60%	40%	-	Amount required within limits permitted
Administrative charges	60%	40%	-	Up to 2% of the project cost.

(Sources:-Ministry of Drinking Water Sanitation, SBM-G Guidelines)

Table No.3 Indicates various head in which funds were utilized as per guideline of SBM-G Managed by Ministry of Drinking water & Sanitation, New Delhi. Core components like SLWM, IEC, Startup activities, Revolving Fund, Construction of Household Toilet, Community Sanitary Complexes, Solid/Liquid Waste Management, Administrative charges as per standard format of Central & State share and also beneficiaries share has been defined in above Table. (Ministry of Drinking water & Sanitation, 2017).

1. Gujarat Declared Free Of Open Defecation A Year Ago. But In 4 Districts, Toilets without Walls, Water and Unconvinced Locals.

As per CAG Reports in selected District of Gujarat State, Like Dang, Jamnagar, Patan, Valsad, Junagadh, Chhotaudepur, Dahod, Banaskantha. They found less coverage or availability of Toilets in Selected Villages in spite of Open Defecation free status and has not built toilet. In spite of Big Budget and IEC still coverage at Ground level is still insufficient for rural household.

There appears to be substantial variation between the government's claims and reality. For instance, in Valsad district's Kaprada taluka (where Mawi lives), 98.73% of the toilets were unused, said the September 2018 CAG report. Of the defunct toilets in Kaprada, only 14.5% were newly constructed and put to use since March 2018. A "significant number" of households were either without toilets or not able to use them because they were incomplete or did not have water, said the CAG report.

They also have mentioned the remarks by Government officials regarding gap between numbers and fact figure check by CAG Officials. They also made remarks on Community Sanitary Complexes and construction of both units to relevant beneficiaries (Shreya R. 2018).

2. Gujarat's case according to Comptroller and Auditor General Report

Comptroller and Auditor General of India is an authority which is highest authority to audit all the expenditure of central government, state government and organizations which are sponsored or financed by the government of India.

In their report of 2018, CAG reports shows for the period of 2014-17, 120 tests checked Gram Panchayats under 8 selected District Panchayats for the period of Last three Years, from the 54008 households 15728 household still did not have any use of toilets which is 29% of total households. The selected district was

already declared Open defecation in 2017 and still huge gap in financial utilization and actual ground reality.

In Valsad District, out of 17,646 only 223 toilets built with financial support under the TSC/NBA were newly built under Swachh Bharat Mission-G while the remaining 17,423 toilets were neglected or were no longer in an operational state. While the process of structure of lasting defunct toilets was under priority. The CAG report finds this response were not tenable as important number of families were either deprived of toilets or not able to practice it for countless details.

Declaring villages Open Defecation Free in India is a complicated matter. With many devout, traditional and caste-based reasons to it, Indians are unfavorable to the foul odor, presence and even verbal mention of fecal. People prefer using water after finishing toilet and Traditional toilets which cannot be constructed without confirming suitable water source. These aspects limit the advanced toilet knowledge that can be used and, thus, many inadequacies of the Swachh Bharat Mission-G agreed toilets external. Individuals often don't choose to usage of these toilets not only preventive the number of toilets built but also interpretation many toilets not in use. As the CAG report references, in 41 of 120 test-checked GPs, families' water networks were not accessible and, consequently, toilets built under SBM continued unused. In 15 villages, toilets were not being used because of non-availability of water and incomplete construction.

While ODF status on paper is an accomplishment, untimely ODF status statement has its own arrangement of unfriendly results. After ODF assertion, the money related sponsorships under SBM are not accessible any longer in any event, for the qualified families and, in this way, the assets should be steered through different plans.

Numerous recipients in regions pronounced ODF on paper, in this way can't get the budgetary endowments under SBM. As per the subjective information gathered in June-July 2017 in Mangrol Block of Junagadh area, around 3,000 family units needed access to toilets and the square had been pronounced ODF much before that. The potential recipients couldn't get assets for building toilets and they were poor to the point that they couldn't develop toilets without budgetary help. While the administration keeps up that CSR supports fill this hole, narrative proof says that the objective is a long way from being accomplished.

Additionally, CSR reserves are not focused and are not legitimately under government control, making them just a likely arrangement that may not generally be dependable (Sumedh M.K 2018).

3. Swachh Bharat Abhiyan: CAG Questions Gujarat Government's Claim on Open Defecation Free Status

The Comptroller and Auditor General (CAG) has said that the government's claim of Gujarat being 'Open Defecation Free'(ODF) appears to be wrong, as many rural households were found to have no toilets. In a survey conducted in eight districts, nearly 30 per cent of houses were found to have no toilets, said the CAG report tabled in the state Assembly on Wednesday (September 19). The Union government had informed the Lok Sabha in February this year that 11 states including Gujarat have been declared as ODF under the Swachh Bharat Mission (SBM).

The survey was conducted in the districts of Dahod, Banaskantha, Chhotaudepur, Dang, Patan, Valsad, Jamnagar and Junagadh. Of the total of 54,008 households in eight districts, 15,728 households had no access to toilets, the CAG said. "Audit observed that the administration had declared all the districts as ODF on achieving the targets set out in the baseline survey conducted in 2012," noted the CAG. "However, this list was not updated after 2012 and therefore, a number of households did not have any access to toilets and they remained uncovered," said the report.

When the issue was raised with the state government in March 2018, the authorities claimed that all the villages are now ODF, as more toilets were built later “through CSR (corporate social responsibility) initiative”. However, the CAG noted, auditors observed that people were still not able to use toilets due to various reasons. In 41 out of the total 120 test-checked villages, the toilets constructed under the Swachh Bharat Mission could not be used as there was no water connection, it said. In 15 villages “toilets were not being used either due to non-availability of water and soak pits or they were incomplete”, the report said. In tribal-dominated Kaprada block of Valsad district, over 17,400 toilets were found to be “defunct”, it said (Press Trust of India 2018).

4. CAG Report picks holes in Gujarat’s Open Defecation free claim

A year after the Gujarat government declared that the state has become open defecation-free (ODF), the Comptroller and Auditor General of India (CAG) in its latest report has dismissed the claim, saying “it does not appear to be correct”. The CAG report, which was tabled in the state Assembly on Wednesday during the two-day monsoon session, stated a survey conducted in 120 gram panchayats in eight districts found that nearly 30 per cent of the households had no access to toilets, either individual or public.

The Union government had informed Lok Sabha in February this year that 11 states, including Gujarat, have been declared as ODF under the Swachh Bharat Mission (SBM). “The state government declared all the districts of Gujarat as ODF by October 2, 2017. However, information provided by 120 test-checked gram panchayats under eight selected district panchayats for the period of 2014-17 revealed that 29 per cent households still did not have access to toilets (individual or public),” the CAG report said. “Therefore, the claim of the state government that all the districts of Gujarat were ODF does not appear to be correct,” it added (Syed K. 2018).

5. Swachh Bharat Mission: It’s all about numbers

We have just a year to go for Swachh Bharat Mission’s (SBM) deadline of making India open-defecation free (ODF). In the last four years, the government has built 86.08 million toilets (as on September 26, 2018) throughout the country as a part of this flagship programme on providing safe sanitation to all by October 2019.

As per the government estimates, sanitation coverage in rural India has increased from 38.7 percent on October 2, 2014, to over 94.01 percent on September 26, 2018. Over 4.73 lakh villages and more than 472 districts have been declared ODF. A large-scale survey by the World Bank on the usage of toilets pegs it at above 90 percent.

As per a report by the United Nations, SBM has played a key role in reducing under-five mortality rates by four points in just a year. Close to 200,000 children under the age of five in India, who would have otherwise lost their lives to treatable diseases like diarrhea, have been saved in two years says the report. Access to safe drinking water and insisting on hand washing, food safety, and the use of toilets to stop open defecation are all factors that have lowered diarrhea deaths, as per the report (Bhaduri A. Purohit M.& Menon A. 2018).

6. In hurry to build 40 toilets a minute, did Government forget about safe sanitation?

The auditor’s surveyed 120 villages in Gujarat’s eight districts—Dahod, Banaskantha, Chhotaudepur, Dang, Patan, Valsad, Jamnagar and Junagadh— during 2014-17. This state, which was declared open-defecation free in October 2017, has 41 such villages where toilets, constructed under the SBM, cannot be used as they have no water connection and 15 villages have no toilets at all, says the report. Also, the auditors add that Gujarat did not update its number of households after the baseline survey of 2012 and an SBM official justifies it saying the extra toilets were constructed under the Corporate Social Responsibility fund.

For example, 17,400 toilets in Kaprada block of Valsad district in Gujarat were defunct, but the SBM officials tagged them as newly-constructed toilets only to be put to use in March 2018. But CAG was not

satisfied as the auditors found that the beneficiaries were not using those toilets owing to non-availability of water or incomplete infrastructure (Sengupta S. 2018).

7. Comptroller and Auditor General of India Report No. 5 Of 2018

To accelerate the efforts to achieve universal sanitation coverage and to put focus on sanitation, the Government of India launched (October 2014) Swachh Bharat Mission. The main objectives of SBM (Gramin) were to improve the levels of cleanliness in rural areas through solid and liquid waste management activities and making GPs Open Defecation Free (ODF), clean and sanitized. In Gujarat, SBM (Gramin) is being implemented by the District Rural Development Agencies (DRDAs).

The SBM guidelines (December 2014) envisage financial assistance up to 12,000 for construction of one unit of Individual Household Latrine (IHHL) to Below Poverty Line (BPL) HHs and identified Above Poverty Line (APL) HHs (restricted to SCs/STs, small and marginal farmers, landless laborers with homestead, physically handicapped and women-headed households). During 2014-17, PRH&RDD received grants of 2,249.53Crore under SBM and could utilize 2,223.56 Crore (99 per cent).

The Assistant Commissioner, SBM (*Gramin*), Gandhinagar accepted (March 2018) that the State has achieved the target of toilet construction set out in baseline survey of 2012, and toilets not covered under baseline survey have been constructed through CSR initiatives. In this regard, inter-district verification and third party verification by Quality Council of India had been completed and all the villages were now ODF.

Information provided by 120 test-checked villages and joint field visits to 30 of 120 test-checked villages revealed the following:

In 41 of 120 villages, household water connections were not available and therefore, toilets constructed under SBM could not be used. In 15 of 30 villages, toilets were not being used either due to non-availability of water and soak pits or they were incomplete.

In Kapradataluka (Valsad district), only 223 (1.26 per cent) of 17,646 toilets constructed with financial assistance (₹ 1,200) under the erstwhile Total Sanitation Campaign/*Nirmal Bharat Abhiyan* were newly constructed under SBM while the remaining 17,423 toilets were in defunct. The Assistant Commissioner, SBM (*Gramin*), Gandhinagar stated (March 2018) that 2,529 of 17,423 defunct toilets had been newly constructed and put to use as of March 2018 while the process of construction of remaining defunct toilets was under progress. Reply is not tenable as a significant number of HHs were either without toilets or not able to use it due to non-availability of water or incomplete structure.

Of the 54,008 households in test-checked villages, only 38,280 households (71 per cent) had access to toilets. Community Sanitary Complexes were available in only 46 of 120 test-checked villages while 8,699

households in the remaining 74 villages did not have any access to toilets (individual or public). Management of solid and liquid waste in 120 test-checked villages was inadequate (CAG, 2018).

Conclusion:

Cleanliness is dream of every citizen and somehow defines our images on global platforms. Unhygienic places to live leads to poor health and poor health are major determinants for low level economic standards. Comparison of Several data with other data is not to challenge the Positive outcomes but to support and up lift the poor part for improvement for actual realization of fact and sense of supporting system for policy maker to take more precise decision.

SBM-G has brought in a remarkable impact and providing benefits to the society at large. It is one of the largest cleanliness drives in the world in terms of Funds and Coverage. It has been reported than till today 9.5 core toilets has been built in India which is huge success for any nation but simultaneously some reports are totally contradict to such fact. Denial of such fact has big question for society too. Construction of toilet is not only the solution but must be monitored regularly whether these are being used by the people at large or not, people are made aware about the importance of using the same and the allied resources are also to be provided with for proper use of toilets under implementation aspect of SBM-G scheme.

Through this present study researchers have tried to touch upon the implementation aspect of allocated fund under SBM-G and its impact on beneficiaries from the state of Gujarat.

References:

1. Ministry of Drinking water & Sanitation. (2017). *Guidelines for Swachh Bharat Mission-Gramin, Government of India. Pp.13-23.New Delhi.*
2. World Health Organization (WHO) and the United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF). (2017) *Progress on Drinking Water, Sanitation and Hygiene: 2017 Update and SDG Baselines. p-37.Geneva.*
3. Ministry of Drinking water & Sanitation. (2017). *Guidelines for Swachh Bharat Mission-Gramin, Government of India. P-32. New Delhi.*
4. Shreya R.(2018). "Gujarat Declared Free Of Open Defecation A Year Ago. But In 4 Districts, Toilets Without Walls, Water And Unconvinced Locals" Retrieved from: www.factchecker.com. 24 Nov, 2018.
5. Sumedh M.K (2018). "ODF status — claims vs. reality of the Swachh Bharat Mission" Retrieved from: www.orfonline.org. 06 oct, 2018.
6. Press Trust of India (2018). "Swachh Bharat Abhiyan: CAG Questions Gujarat Government's Claim On Open Defecation Free Status" Retrived from:www.swachhindia.ndtv.com. 22 September, 2018.
7. Syed K. (2018). "CAG report picks holes in Gujarat's Open Defecation-free claim" Retrieved from: www.indianexpress.com. on 21 September, 2018.
8. Bhaduri A. Purohit M.& Menon A. (2018). "Swachh Bharat Mission: It's all about numbers" Retrieved from: www.indiawaterportal.org. on 2 October, 2018.
9. Sengupta S. (2018). "In hurry to build 40 toilets a minute, did government forget about safe sanitation?" Retrieved from: www.downtoearth.org.in on 21 September, 2018.
10. Comptroller and Auditor general of India. (2018). "Local bodies for the year ended March 2017." New Delhi.

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